

Site: Sphinx Temple Season 80

Area: N. Colonnade Square R16 Locus Number LEVEL 3 7/1/80

Progress of Excavation This level is thought to be fill from previous excavation. This unconsolidated loose sand fill, w/ few shreds abuts against Level 4

8/1/80: M. Lehner; continued clearing

at ③ at S end of trench where ③ fills square pillar socket cutting.

Here, at E Bolk, in socket, small dumb stones - looks more sandy. Left and designated ③a. Also trimmed balks. Balk

trimming and ③ removal - no sifting, or samples. Few small sherd frags, alabaster, granite frags from ③ saved. ③ continues to show

mod. paper etc. * Believe clean sand layer and darker brown humidified sand under it below removed as ③

Locus Description a clean yellow sand layer extending under Level 3 from the edge of the trench at approx 12 cm from the north wall. Pieces of newspaper were recovered & fragments of calcit

15 level ③?

Location in Square along north wall of trench # Level 3 extends from West wall to approx 60 cm East of W wall

Under Locus _____ Over Locus Humidified dk brown sand

Locus Dimensions _____

Levels _____

Analysis of non-artifactual materials _____